

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF MICRONIZED PROGESTERONE AND CLOMIPHENE CITRATE FOR THE SUPPRESSION OF PREMATURE OVULATION

Khalilova M.M.

Assistant at Fergana Public Health Medical Institute

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Summary . High relevance and The widespread use of in vitro fertilization in the field of modern reproductology has led to the development of many methods for conducting IVF. As a result, thorough processing and analysis of data is required to determine the most effective method of in vitro fertilization . This article examines variations of IVF using clomiphene citrate and micronized progesterone and examines the differences in their effectiveness.

words : clomiphene citrate, micronized progesterone, LH surge, premature luteinization , IVF/ICSI, with ovarian stimulation , oocytes and blastocyst formation .

Introduction

The field of in vitro fertilization (IVF) has been successfully expanding year by year and aims to provide safe and effective services to increase pregnancy and live birth rates ¹ . The success of ART depends on adequate follicle recruitment (oocyte number) and follicle development (oocyte quality) ² . Many factors, such as a woman's age, weight, ovarian reserve and endocrine conditions, impact follicle recruitment during ovarian stimulation ³ . The goal of ovarian stimulation for ART through the giving of exogenous gonadotropins (GN) is to increase circulating serum FSH levels above a threshold that causes the growth of 10–15 follicles rather than a single dominant follicle as in the natural cycle ⁴ .

The administration of gonadotropins for ovarian stimulation has significantly improved the success of IVF, but has faced the serious problem of premature luteinizing hormone (LH) release and subsequent luteinization before ovarian follicle maturation , which is associated with poor oocyte quality, decreased fertilization and implantation rates ⁵ . Premature LH surge is a leading cause of cycle cancellation during controlled ovarian stimulation in women undergoing IVF/ICSI and can put the risk oocyte yield ⁶ . Accompaniment administration of a gonadotropin- releasing hormone (GnRH) agonist or antagonist in controlled ovarian stimulation (COS) protocols is used to prevent premature release of LH, and final maturation of oocytes and ovulation caused by bolus administration of an agonist GnRH , human chorionic gonadotropin

(HCG) or both to improve response and produce good quality oocytes and embryos with maximum implantation and pregnancy rates ⁷.

Clomiphene Citrate Protocol (CC) has been the most widely used fertility booster four decades and is an estrogen agonist/antagonist that blocks estrogen receptors in the pituitary gland and reduces the normal decline in follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) production, dramatically reducing cost but resulting in similar pregnancy rates, as with the usual IVF protocol ⁸. Clomiphene citrate is an analogue of the non-steroidal estrogenic compound chlorotrianisene, which acts as a selective estrogen receptor modulator ¹. It is also able to stimulate and increase the secretion of endogenous pituitary GN, and have a direct effect on the ovaries, making granulosa cells more sensitive to pituitary gonadotropins ⁹.

Because CC is a potent FSH stimulator, adding it to the early follicular phase of conventional ovarian stimulation with exogenous GN may increase serum FSH concentrations, leading to higher follicle recruitment and oocyte yield at oocyte retrieval ¹⁰.

Micronized progesterone protocol is a new ovarian stimulation strategy used in recent years, which is also called the progesterone ovarian stimulation (PPOS) protocol ¹. This protocol has been reported to prevent spontaneous luteinizing hormone (LH) surges and premature ovulation in an IVF program. It provides an alternative treatment for people with poor response ³. However, research into the differences between the two ovarian stimulation strategies is sparse.

In this study, we tried to compare the effectiveness of protocols using Clomiphene citrate and micronized progesterone in patients included in IVF/ICSI protocols at the Siz IVF Center Ona Bo`lasiz ". The primary objective of this study was to compare the number of recovered oocytes, metaphase II (MII) oocytes, and viable embryos.

Research methods. The study involved 164 patients who underwent examination and preparation for in vitro fertilization at the IVF Center from November 2022 to December 2023. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki for medical research. All participants provided informed consent after counseling regarding infertility treatment and IVF procedures.

The selected patients were divided into two groups: the main group consisted of 126 patients using **micronized progesterone**; the comparison group consisted of 38 patients using **clomiphene citrate**. There were no

significant differences in baseline characteristics, indications for IVF, previous IVF failures, or baseline hormonal profiles between the two groups. AMH levels in the study groups were the same 1.3 ± 0.7 .

To participate, patients had to meet the following criteria: (1) age not older than 40 years, (2) presence of regular menstrual cycles within the previous 3 months (lasting 25–35 days), (3) antral follicle count (AFC) more than 3 per 2–3 days of the menstrual cycle and (4) basal FSH concentration in the blood serum not more than 10 IU/l.

Exclusion criteria were: (1) age <18 or >40 years; (2) baseline serum FSH level >10 IU/L or absence of antral follicles on ultrasound; (3) PCOS; (4) endometriosis grade 3 or higher; (5) the presence of contraindications to therapy for ovarian stimulation.

In the comparison group, CC 100 mg/day CC was started with gonadotropins on the 2-3rd day of the cycle every day to stimulate late follicular development before the trigger day. At the same time, transvaginal ultrasound was performed. In the main group, **micronized progesterone** (utrozhestan) 200 mg was administered daily from the 2-3rd day of the cycle for a follicle size of 14 mm. The final stage of oocyte maturation in both groups was stimulated with triptorelin (0.1 mg) or human chorionic gonadotropin. Oocyte collection was carried out 35-36 hours after identification of one or more follicles with an average diameter of 18 mm in both groups. Before oocyte collection, the presence of dominant follicles was confirmed using transvaginal ultrasound. Oocyte retrieval was performed under internal anesthesia with a 19-G single-lumen aspiration needle. All follicles >10 mm in diameter were extracted. The resulting oocytes were fertilized using IVF/ICSI. All premium quality embryos (including 6-10 cell blastomere Grade I and Grade II embryos) were vitrified frozen on day 5 after oocyte retrieval.

The groups were compared based on the number of oocytes recovered, metaphase II (MII) oocytes, and viable embryos. The primary outcomes in this study were the number of oocytes, MII oocytes, and viable embryos recovered.

Statistical analysis was carried out using RStudio. Student's t-test was used to compare the means of the dependent variables. The significance level was set to $\alpha=0.05$.

Results and discussion. n =165 patients were analyzed in this analysis. The main group consisted of n = 127 (77.6%) patients using micronized progesterone, and the comparison group consisted of n = 38 (23.4 %) patients using clomiphene citrate. Baseline characteristics of the patients are shown in

Table 1 . There were no significant differences between the two groups in baseline characteristics, indications for IVF, previous IVF failures, and baseline hormonal profiles.

Table 1. Basic characteristics of women participating in the study undergoing IVF/ICSI treatment.

Characteristic	Main group (n=127)	Comparison group (n = 38)	P value
Age (years), mean ± standard deviation	29.7 ± 5.5	30.4 ± 4.8	0.4784
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ± standard deviation	24.0 ± 4.3	24, 2 ± 3, 7	0.8387
Duration of infertility (years), mean ± standard deviation	4.9 ± 4.1	3.6 ± 3.5	0.1141
Primary infertility, n (%)	74 (58, 2%)	18 (48, 4)	0.4564
Pipe factor	49 (38.5 %)	22 (58, 1%)	0.0906
Male factor	44 (35.2%)	11 (29.0 %)	0.6861
Idiopathic infertility	17.78 (14.3 %)	7 (19.4 %)	0.6999
Previous IVF failures, n (%)	8.3(6.6%)	3 (6.5%)	0.999

Table 2 shows the characteristics of the controlled ovarian stimulation cycle. According to table No. 2 and diagrams 1 and 2, the average number of oocytes recovered from patients of the main group (21.4 ±9.3) was significantly higher than the same value (11.2 ±4.6) in the comparison group (p <0.01). The average number of oocytes in metaphase II was also higher in the main group: 15.6±6.7 versus 7.9 ±3.7 (p<0.01). The number of fertilized oocytes was significantly higher in the main group (13.6 ± 5.7) than in the comparison group (7.1 ± 3.5) (p<0.01).

Table 2. Controlled Ovarian Stimulation Cycle Characteristics

Characteristic	Main group (n = 127)	Comparison group (n = 38)	P-value
Oocytes received (n)	21.4 ± 9.34	11.2 ± 4.63	<0.001
MII oocytes (n)	15.6 ± 6.56	7.9 ± 3.67	<0.001
Fertilized oocytes 2PN(n)	13.6 ± 5,7	7.1± 3.5	<0.001

Characteristic	Main group (n = 127)	Comparison group (n = 38)	P-value
Fragmented embryos (n)	7.1 ± 3.6	3.64 ± 2.4	<0.001
Wed. Percentage of quality of mature oocytes	102.12 ± 2.24	93.48 ± 5.6	0.01
Wed. number of high quality embryos	5.09 ± 0.3	2.88 ± 0.3	<0.001
Wed. number of average-quality embryos	3.84 ± 0.14	1.01 ± 0.18	<0.001
Wed. number of low quality embryos	1.98 ± 0.13	1.26 ± 0.23	<0.001
Ratio of high quality embryos per number of mature oocytes (MII)	54.02	58.672	>0.01
Ratio of average quality embryos to the number of mature oocytes (MII)	19.08	16.21	>0.01
Ratio of low quality embryos per number of mature oocytes (MII)	25.03	19.456	>0.01

Diagram No. 1 Average number of obtained oocytes and oocytes in metaphase 2

Diagram No. 2 Average percentage of oocyte quality

Micronized progesterone

Clomiphene citrate

Diagram No. 3. Correlation between the average number of embryos when using micronized and clomiphene citrate

As shown in the correlation diagram in diagram No. 3, the average number of embryos in all three groups, in the main group treated with Micronized progesterone, statistically significantly prevails over the control group taking the drug Clomiphene Citrate. From the data in Table No. 2 it is clear that in the percentage of embryos in the group using micronized progesterone there is a slight statistically insignificant improvement than in the control group using Clomiphene Quote . The number of viable embryos recovered in the micronized progesterone group was also greater than in the Clomiphene Citrate group, with mean values of 3.3 ± 0.3 versus 1.9 ± 0.3 ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions

According to the results of our study, micronized progesterone is superior to clomiphene citrate in producing more oocytes and metaphase II (MII) oocytes . In addition, the results of the study showed the predominance of micronized progesterone in the average number of embryos in all groups of their quality in relation to the drug Clomiphene Citrate. The percentage of high-quality embryos in both groups showed similar results.

This retrospective controlled study showed that micronized progesterone is an effective oral alternative for preventing premature LH surge in women undergoing IVF cycles. These data will help develop a new regimen of ovarian stimulation in combination with embryo cryopreservation . Further blinded randomized controlled studies are needed to confirm the feasibility of this regimen, the optimal dose, types and long-term safety of drugs used in IVF.

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